

PROTOCOL FOR COLLECTION OF DATA TO IDENTIFY SUSTAINABILITY HOTSPOTS AND DATA GAPS WITHIN THE CALIMERO PROJECT

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GLOSSARY

LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
CF	Characterization factor
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint

1 INTRODUCTION

The present document describes the procedure for data collection of the current industry practices within the CALIMERO project, aiming to identify and analyze the environmental, social, and economic impacts associated with the European bio-based industrial sectors. This document also sets up the structure for quantifying the sustainability impacts for the industries involved in the project.

The industrial sectors involved in the project include construction, woodworking, textile, pulp and paper, and bio-chemicals.

With regards to the environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), the protocol follows the ISO 14040/44 and Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology according to the European Commission (2021)¹. Regarding the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), products and organisations' social life cycle assessment guidelines are followed (Benoît Norris et al., 2020). For the Life Cycle Costing (LCC), no specific guidelines are followed but the procedure follows the same principles as the ISO 14040/44.

1.1 Participants in data collection and their roles

IVL will have the overarching responsibilities of the data collection. The data collection, the literature review for data gaps, as well as the Life Cycle Impact Assessment will then be divided by sector among the project partners as follows:

- IVL: bio-chemicals, pulp and paper industries
- LIST: textile industry
- Neovili: textile industry
- CTA: woodworking industry
- WeLOOP: construction industry

1 METHODS FOR DATA COLLECTION

1.1 Project partners for data collection

The data will be collected from the project partners, including the following actors and sectors (responsible project partner indicated in brackets):

- ECIA; construction industry (WeLOOP responsible)
- CESFOR; woodworking industry (CTA responsible)
- TECHTERA; textile industry (LIST/Neovili responsible)
- EREKS; textile industry (LIST/Neovili responsible)
- ESSITY; pulp and paper industry (IVL responsible)
- BIMKEMI; biochemical industry (IVL responsible)

1.2 Order of prioritization for data collection

Data collection will be based on the following order of prioritization, based on partners' availability and previous assessments, when available:

1. Primary data collection specific for the project,
2. Data from previous LCA, LCC and/or S-LCA studies with the project partners on sustainability impacts,
3. Data from the project partners' reporting on sustainability, e.g. in annual accounts,
4. Complementary interviews with project partners,

¹ Available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/recommendation-use-environmental-footprint-methods_en

5. Data from literature surveys on environmental, social and economic impacts.

1.3 Data quality

The collected data should be of highest quality possible in terms of technological, geographical and time-related representativeness, as well as completeness, precision/uncertainty, methodological appropriateness and consistency. For each of these criteria, the data quality will be evaluated in later steps on the CALIMERO project. For example, primary data collected for environmental LCA should reflect the production of the project partners within the last three years (2020 to 2022). Collected data that will be used for LCAs carried out within the project will meet the data quality requirements of the PEF methodology (European Commission, 2021).

1.4 System boundaries for data collection

Life cycle stages from cradle to grave will be considered in the data collection from the project partners, including the following ones:

- Raw material extraction
- Primary production
- Capital goods and maintenance of these
- Processing
- Packaging
- Transportation (for relevant processes, pre-gate)

Further, data will consider the overall outputs of the partners. Data collection will be completed by collecting some scenarios for downstream (transport to client, installation, use and end of life).

1.5 Data collection of industry current practices

1.5.1 Environmental accounts

Please see the attached Excel file for a template for data collection.

1.5.2 Economic accounts

The data used in the LCA will also be used as the basis for the LCC. All cost data should be expressed in USD, and currency conversion should be disclosed when needed. Both fixed and operational costs of the product system will be considered. Fixed costs are independent of whether processes are operated or not and include investment costs, maintenance costs, cost of staff and other costs such as permit costs, other contracted costs and R&D costs. The staff cost covers the number of full-time employees, and the cost should reflect site and country-specific conditions. The variable costs depend on whether processes are operated, including costs for raw materials, energy and auxiliaries, waste management costs and transportation. Additionally, revenues from products and co-products are included. Cost for carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions will be included. Other externalities will be excluded.

Different inflation rates and discount rates will be elaborated upon to test the sensitivity of the choice.

When collecting cost data, reference year should be indicated in the data collection.

1.5.3 Social assessment

Primary data for social LCA will be collected through an online survey. The questionnaire is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Questions included in the survey for social LCA.

Q1. Please indicate the organisation to which you are affiliated:
Q2. Please indicate your position's title (e.g., research & development):
Q3. Please indicate the region(s) in which your organisation is located.
<i>Answer Choices</i>
Europe
Asia
North America
Central America
South America
Africa
Oceania
If possible, please mention your country / countries of activity below.
Q4. Please indicate the bio-based sector you are working in (or that you are the most familiar with). The remaining questions below relate to the supply chain for the sector selected here.
<i>Answer Choices</i>
Construction
Textile
Woodworking
Pulp & paper
Biochemistry
Other (please specify)
Q5. Please indicate which step(s) of the life cycle of bio-based process for the selected supply chain you are familiar with (depending on your knowledge of the selected supply chain). For example, if you know the organisation providing your business with biologically sourced raw materials, your evaluation will include the relevance of different social aspects for the production of such raw materials.
<i>Answer Choices</i>
Production of raw biological/organic materials (e.g., cotton, wood)
Production of additives / auxiliary materials (e.g., inorganic chemicals)
Transformation & manufacturing processes
Use by consumers (including maintenance & use of additional consumables)
End-of-life activities (collection, reuse, recycling, incineration or landfilling)

Supporting activities : Policy, NGO, consumer organisation & other professional support (e.g., consultant)
Transport & logistics
Other (please specify)
Q6. Please evaluate the relevance of stakeholder categories for the selected supply chain: In S-LCA, a stakeholder category is a group type that can be affected by the activities of organizations involved in the life cycle of the product, service or organisation under consideration.
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
EMPLOYEES/WORKERS (for any step of the supply chain)
LOCAL COMMUNITIES (in direct contact with any step of the supply chain)
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS (actors with direct interest in bio-based products, e.g. suppliers)
CONSUMERS (B2B & B2C)
SOCIETY (in a global sense)
CHILDREN (in contact with the supply chain, e.g., education in local community, exposition to marketing, or as consumers)
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q7. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Employees/Workers for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Freedom of association and collective bargaining
Child labour
Fair salary
Working hours
Forced labour
Equal opportunities/ discrimination
Health and Safety
Social benefits / social security
Employment relationship
Sexual harassment
Smallholders including farmers
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q8. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Local Communities for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Access to material resources

Access to immaterial resources
Delocalization and migration
Cultural heritage
Safe & healthy living conditions
Respect of indigenous rights
Community engagement
Local employment
Secure living conditions
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q9. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Value Chain Actors for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Fair competition
Promoting social responsibility
Supplier relationships
Respect intellectual property rights
Wealth distribution
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q10. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Consumers for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Health & safety
Feedback/grievance mechanism
Consumer privacy
Transparency
End of life responsibility
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q11. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Society for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Public commitments to sustainability issues
Contribution to economic development
Prevention & mitigation of armed conflicts
Technology development
Corruption

Ethical treatment of animals
Poverty alleviation
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q12. Please evaluate the relevance of the sub-categories below to Children for the selected supply chain:
<i>Answers: Rating between Highly relevant, relevant, slightly relevant, not relevant, N/A</i>
Education provided in the local community
Health issues for children as consumers
Children concerns regarding marketing practices
Other (please specify) and/or your comments
Q13. If you believe there are particularly critical hotspots (positive or negative) in the selected supply chain, please briefly describe them below (stakeholder, impact, step of supply chain, localisation, etc.)
Q14. Are you aware of any relevant social issue that it was not mentioned in any of the previous questions? Or do you foresee new social issues for the future? Please provide a short description below.
Q15. If you would like us to contact you for additional discussion, or to provide us with some more details, please write your e-mail address below.
Q16. Please rate the difficulty of this survey.
<i>Answers: Rating between Easy, medium, difficult</i>
Q17. By ticking the "I agree" box below, I agree that my answers to the survey are collected, treated and used within the CALIMERO project.

1.6 Goal and scope

1.6.1 Functional unit/reference flow

Functional units for each case study will be defined further on.

1.6.2 Cut-off rules

Cut-off for environmental sustainability assessment will follow the PEF guidelines (European Commission, 2021). With regards to the social and economic sustainability assessments, cut-off rules will be defined further on.

1.6.3 Allocation rules

Allocation will be carried out according to the PEF guidelines (European Commission, 2021).

1.7 Environmental impacts

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1.7.1 Impact categories and impact assessment methods

The impact categories and methods recommended by the European Commission (2021)² for environmental life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) within the PEF are listed in Table 2. Additionally, climate change is divided into impacts from fossil, biogenic and land use change sources.

Table 2. Impact categories and methods recommended by the European Commission (2021) within the PEF.

Impact category	Indicator	Unit	Recommended LCIA method
Climate change, fossil	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)
Climate change, biogenic	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)
Climate change, land use change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential	kg CFC-11 eq	EDIP model based on the ODPs of the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) over an infinite time horizon (WMO 2014 + i ntegrations)
Human cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh	USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018)
Human toxicity, non-cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh	USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018)
Particulate matter	Impact on human health	Disease incidence	PM method recommended by UNEP (Fantke et al., 2016 in UNEP 2016)
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ²³⁵	kBq U ²³⁵ eq	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995 (Frischknecht et al, 2000)
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq	LOTOS-EUROS model (Van Zelm et al, 2008) as implemented in ReCiPe 2008
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H+ eq	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N eq	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009) as implemented in ReCiPe
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009) as implemented in ReCiPe
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	CTUe	USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018

²Available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/recommendation-use-environmental-footprint-methods_en

Land use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil quality index • Biotic production • Erosion resistance • Mechanical filtration • Groundwater replenishment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dimensionless (pt) • kg biotic production • kg soil • m³ water • m³ groundwater 	Soil quality index based on LANCA model (De Laurentiis et al. 2019) and on the LANCA CF version 2.5 (Horn and Maier, 2018)
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	m ³ world _{eq}	Available WATER REMaining (AWARE) model (Boulay et al., 2018; UNEP 2016)
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb _{eq}	van Oers et al., 2002 as in CML 2002 method, v.4.8
Resource use, fossils	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ	van Oers et al., 2002 as in CML 2002 method, v.4.8

1.7.2 Additional impacts

1.7.2.1 *Biodiversity*

We aim to assess the existing and under-development biodiversity methods. Different methods will be evaluated by partners to check for the needed data to be collected. More information to be added further on in the project if needed.

1.7.2.2 *Direct human exposure impacts*

The PEF list does not include a category for direct human exposure-related impacts from chemicals. Two methods of potential interest here are Usetox3 and ProScale.

1.7.2.3 *Criticality indicators*

We aim to develop a criticality method for biobased materials. Partners will identify and assess different methods to check for the needed data to be collected.

1.8 **Social impacts (hotspots)**

1.8.1 Impact categories and impact assessment methods

1.1.1.1 *Methodology for S-LCA*

The SLCA is based on the UNEP Guidelines, the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) using the following social impact categories and sub-categories (Table 3).

Table 3. Stakeholders' categories and impact sub-categories within SLCA based on the UNEP Guidelines.

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORIES	IMPACT SUB-CATEGORIES
EMPLOYEE/ WORKER	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Freedom of association and collective bargaining 2. Child labour 3. Fair salary 4. Working hours 5. Forced labour 6. Equal opportunities/discrimination 7. Health and safety 8. Social benefits / social security 9. Employment relationship 10. Sexual harassment 11. Smallholders, including farmers
LOCAL COMMUNITY	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to material resources

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Access to immaterial resources 3. Delocalisation and migration 4. Cultural heritage 5. Safe and healthy living conditions 6. Respect of indigenous rights 7. Community engagement 8. Local employment 9. Secure living conditions
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fair competition 2. Promoting social responsibility 3. Supplier relationships 4. Respect of intellectual property rights 5. Wealth distribution
CONSUMER	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health and safety 2. Feedback mechanism 3. Consumer privacy 4. Transparency 5. End-of-life responsibility
SOCIETY	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public commitments to sustainability issues 2. Contribution to economic development 3. Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts 4. Technology development 5. Corruption 6. Ethical treatment of animals 7. Human rights 8. Poverty alleviation
CHILDREN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education provided in the local community 2. Health issues for children as consumers 3. Children's concerns regarding marketing

2 REFERENCES

BENOÎT NORRIS, C., TRAVERZO, M., NEUGEBAUER, S., EKENER, E., SCHAUBROECK, T. & RUSSO GARRIDO, S. 2020. Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. United Nations Environment Programme.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2021. Commission Recommendation on the Use of the Environmental Footprint Methods to Measure and Communicate the Life Cycle Environmental Performance of Products and Organisations. Brussels, Belgium.